

Studies on Some Monofluophosphates. Part I

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Monofluophosphates of cadmium, manganese, nickel, chromium(III), and iron (III) have been prepared and analysed. Compositions of the compounds are found to correspond to $\text{CdPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{NiPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{Fe}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$; their crystals have been found to be isomorphous with the corresponding sulphates.

If one of the hydroxyl radicals on the phosphoric acid molecule is replaced by isosteric fluorine radical, monofluophosphoric acid molecule can be obtained. This acid is both isoelectronic and isoprotic with the sulphuric acid. Pentavalent positively charged phosphorus ion has the same ionic radius as that of hexavalent positively charged sulphur ion, i.e. $0.34 \text{ \AA}$. Negatively charged fluorine and oxygen ions have approximately equal ionic radii, namely $1.33 \text{ \AA}$ and $1.32 \text{ \AA}$ respectively. Both the ions are bivalent and have thirtytwo peripheral electrons. It is expected therefore that monofluophosphoric acid and its salts should be similar in properties to sulphuric acid and its salts.

Weinland and Alpha¹ tried to prepare potassium, rubidium, and caesium monofluophosphates of the formula $\text{ROP}(\text{OH})_2\text{F}$. Werner considered them not as true fluophosphates but as additive compounds of hydrofluoric acid and orthophosphates having the formula $\text{RH}_2\text{PO}_3 \cdot \text{HF}$. Lange² prepared monofluophosphates of a few alkali and alkaline earth metals. Ray³ in his note on isomorphism and chemical homology reported the preparation of a few monofluophosphates and their double salts by Sarkar. Goswami⁴ reported the isolation of monofluophosphates of copper, cobalt, nickel, and zinc and found them isomorphous with the corresponding sulphates. Lange and Stein⁵ studied the equilibrium in aqueous solution between H_3PO_4 and HF. Lange and Krueger⁷ prepared dimethyl and diethyl esters of monofluophosphoric acid and noted its toxic effect. Several di-esters of monofluophosphoric acid of the formula:

1. Goldschmidt, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 282.
2. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1899, 21, 43.
3. *Ber.*, 1929, 62B, 793.
4. *Nature*, 1930, 126, 310
5. *This Journal*, 1937, 14, 660.
6. *Ber.*, 1931, 64B, 2772.
7. *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1598.

were isolated and used during the last world war as highly toxic war gas⁸. The use of the less toxic esters was also reported as insecticides and in medicine. Lange and Livingstone⁹ synthesised anhydrous monofluorophosphoric acid from anhydrous metaphosphoric acid and anhydrous hydrofluoric acid. Recently Donald and his co-workers¹⁰ studied the single liquid phase system $H_2O-HF-P_2O_5$ and determined nine structural entities with NMR spectroscopy. Kihl and Montel¹¹ studied the hydrolysis of $CaPO_3F \cdot 2H_2O$. Kihl¹² also investigated the thermal decomposition of alkaline earth monofluorophosphates and studied their X-ray photographs.

In the present investigation, monofluorophosphates of certain bi- and tri-valent metals have been prepared. Their compositions have been established by analysis and by their absorption spectra in infrared and ultraviolet regions. Attempts have been made to study their stabilities by recording the dissociation pressures at different temperatures and calculating the heat of dissociation with the help of the Clapeyron-Clausius equation. Isothermal dissociation pressure-composition curves have been studied to ascertain the number of stable hydrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium monofluorophosphate was obtained by heating trisodium metaphosphate¹³ with sodium fluoride; silver monofluorophosphate was prepared by the method suggested by Audrieth¹⁵. Monofluorophosphates of Cd, Mn, Ni, Cr(III), and Fe(III) were prepared from silver monofluorophosphate and the chloride of the metal by metathesis according to the equations:

Extra pure quality of the metal chloride was dissolved in the least quantity of water and was cooled in a refrigerator. A thin cream of an equimolecular quantity of silver monofluorophosphate in distilled water, also cooled, was run slowly with stirring into the cooled chloride solution. Precipitated silver chloride was removed by filtration. The filtrate was tested for silver and chloride ions; the excess of one or the other was removed by careful addition of a very dilute solution of either chloride or silver monofluorophosphate. Silver chloride, thus precipitated, was filtered. The filtrate was allowed to crystallise in vacuum over H_2SO_4 or by spontaneous evaporation.

Cadmium Monofluorophosphate, $CdPO_3F \cdot 8/3 H_2O$, forms monoclinic transparent crystals, diamagnetic in nature and isomorphous with $CdSO_4 \cdot 8/3 H_2O$. Its sp. gravity was

8. Sartori, *Chem. Rev.*, 1951, 48, 225.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 49, 1073.

10. Donald *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, 81, 8350.

11. *Compt. rend.*, 1960, 250, 131.

12. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1962, 2, 1406.

13. *Inorganic Analysis*, Vol. III, ed. L. F. Audrieth, 1950, p. 104, Mc.Graw Hill Publication Inc.

14. *Ibid.*, p. 106.

15. *Ibid.*, p. 109.

determined as 3.08 from which molecular volume was calculated as 83.8, nearly the same as that of $\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (83.09). Unlike cadmium sulphate, it is sparingly soluble in water and practically insoluble in organic solvents. It dissolves in mineral acids with decomposition into orthophosphate and fluoride. It is more soluble in cadmium sulphate solution from which mixed crystals have been obtained.

Manganese monofluophosphate, $\text{MnPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, forms very fine monoclinic pink crystals, which are strongly paramagnetic and isomorphous with $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Sp. gravity of freshly crystallised sample was found to be 2.11 from which its molecular volume was calculated as 106.6, very close to that of $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (105.5). Unlike manganese sulphate, it is sparingly soluble in water and practically insoluble in organic solvents. It is decomposed by mineral acids to orthophosphate and fluoride. It is efflorescent and loses weight rapidly in the atmosphere. The solubility of the salt is greater in manganese sulphate solution from which mixed crystals have been obtained.

Nickel monofluophosphate, $\text{NiPO}_3\text{F} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, forms bluish green, needle-shaped, rhombic prisms, which are strongly paramagnetic and are isomorphous with $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Sp. gravity and molecular volume were found to be 1.95 and 145.1 respectively (mol. vol. of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 144.2). It is soluble in water. The aqueous solution formed a precipitate of BiPO_3F when treated with BaCl_2 solution, though the precipitation was not complete. It effloresces and provides the yellow anhydrous salt when heated. Its colour changes from bluish green to green above 55° . Mixed crystals were obtained with nickel sulphate.

Chromium (III) Monofluophosphate.—The resulting filtrate on spontaneous evaporation for 2-3 weeks deposited dark green (not violet), octahedral plates. The crystals were dried between the folds of filter papers; immediate analysis of the crystals corresponded to $\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$. When exposed to air for a few weeks, the salt provided a lower hydrate, corresponding approximately to $\text{Cr}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The salt is paramagnetic in nature. Sp. gravity and the molecular volume were found to be 1.7 and 424.5 respectively. The latter is comparable with that of $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (421.5). The salt is slightly soluble in water, but the solubility decreases on dehydration. It is insoluble in organic solvents and is decomposed by mineral acids. Mixed crystals were obtained with chromium sulphate.

Iron(III) monofluophosphate, $\text{Fe}_2(\text{PO}_3\text{F})_3 \cdot 12 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, forms pink crystals, which are strongly paramagnetic. The sp. gravity and the molecular volume are 2.2 and 282.5 respectively. It is sparingly soluble in water and insoluble in organic solvents. It is decomposed by mineral acids and loses water when exposed to air. Mixed crystals with ferric sulphate could not be prepared.

Monofluophosphate ion, PO_3F^{2-} , did not respond to the analytical reaction of either fluoride or orthophosphate ions. Although the normal salts of monofluophosphoric acid are similar in nature to the corresponding salts of sulphuric acid, the usual procedure applied for gravimetric determination of sulphates are not applicable to the determination of monofluophosphates. These salts were therefore converted to orthophosphate and fluoride, which were analysed separately. Phosphorous was estimated as $\text{Mg}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, gravimetrically. The presence of phosphate in monofluophosphate is a source of considerable trouble for the analysis of fluoride. Fluorine was estimated after its careful isolation from interfering phosphate by distillation with perchloric acid as hydrofluosilicic acid and

titrating it against a standard thorium nitrate solution, using 1% aqueous solution of sodium alizarin sulphonate¹⁶ as indicator.

Silver was estimated as silver chloride gravimetrically. Cadmium was estimated as cadmium oxinate¹⁷. The pH^{18} was maintained at about 5.4; the precipitate was dried to a constant weight at about 180° and weighed as $Cd(C_9H_6ON)_2$. Manganese was estimated by bismuthate method volumetrically. Nickel was estimated as dimethyl glyoximate. The precipitate was heated to a constant weight at $120-30^{\circ}$. Chromium was estimated by oxidising it to chromate and then adding measured excess of standard ferrous salt and titrating the excess with standard $KMnO_4$ solution. Analytical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

S $\ddot{e}$ lts.	% Phosphorus.		% Fluorine.		% Metal.	
	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Ag_2PO_3F	9.75	9.88	6.08	6.06	68.60	68.70
$CdPO_3F \cdot 8/3 H_2O$	12.01	11.99	7.22	7.35	43.62	43.50
$MnPO_3F \cdot 4 H_2O$	13.63	13.77	8.59	8.49	24.31	24.42
$NiPO_3F \cdot 7 H_2O$	10.98	10.96	6.80	6.72	20.74	20.76
$Cr_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 18H_2O$	12.79	12.87	7.95	7.89	14.37	14.40
$Fe_2(PO_3F)_3 \cdot 12 H_2O$	14.92	14.95	9.30	9.17	17.99	17.98

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16. Reynolds and Hill, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1939, 11, 21.
17. Berg, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 321.
18. Borrel and Paris, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 6, 389.
19. Duval, *ibid.*, 1950, 4, 197.